

THE STUDY OF BONDED REPAIR TECHNOLOGY ON CRACKED COMPOSITE STRUCTURE UNDER BIAXIAL LOADING

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ABSTRACT

The finite element analysis of bonded repair technology has been developed and applied to repair cracked aircraft composite components by using the laminated composite patch. This report is to discuss the performance of bonded repair on an unidirectional composite plate with inclined central through crack by using the strain energy density theory. For better repair efficiency, the results show that the ply orientation is arranged to slightly coincide with the maximum principle tensile stress or is perpendicular to the crack. Also, the stacking sequence does not affect the repair results significantly.

INTRODUCTION

The use of advanced composite materials, especially graphite/epoxy composites, for aircraft structures have been expanding rapidly in recent years. The reason for using composite materials in place of metals is that substantial weight savings can be achieved because of their superior strength-to-weight, stiffness-to-weight ratios and better fatigue resistance compared with the conventional materials of aircraft construction such as aluminum alloys. Advanced composite structures were first introduced on military aircraft when the reduced weight was desired to improve tactical performance. Commercial aircraft manufacturers are also beginning to use composites in structural applications where reduced structural weight leads to significant fuel savings [1,2]. In practice these materials may contain defects such as cracks, voids and delaminations produced by either fatigue, impact damage or poor design. Their initiation and propagation to form cracks are very common. A cost-effective extension of the safe life of an aircraft may be accomplished by reinforcing the cracked components. The concept of bonded repair is to change the load path and bypass the defects. Hence a significant reduction of stress intensity factors or energy level near the crack tip will be reached.

Conventional fracture mechanics deals with homogeneous isotropic materials has been highly successful. With the increasing use of materials with directional properties, analyses of anisotropic elasticity become interesting [3,4,5]. Over the last two decades, considerable effort has been spent in the development of adhesively bonded repairs to increase the fatigue life of cracked components made by metal [6,7] or composite [8]. But most of these studies only discussed simple mode I problem. Since most of the structural components are subjected to biaxial loading during flight and all cracks are not align the principal directions, the biaxial

loading will have a significant effect on the behavior of crack growth and fracture. This paper studies the elastic stress analysis of bonding the composite patches on an unidirectional graphite/epoxy panel with an inclined central crack under biaxial loading. The optimization of selecting the patch fiber orientation at different biaxial load ratios and the effects of patch shapes and laminate stacking sequence on design have been emphasized. Due to the material discontinuity and geometry complexity, the mixed mode crack problems are analysed by use of the three-dimensional finite element method combined with the strain energy density criterion.

METHOD OF ANALYSIS

Because of the mathematical difficulties posed by three-dimensional elasticity, the theoretical determination of the nature of singularity at the crack front has not been completely solved. The local stress field near the crack front, even at the free surface, is assumed to be in a state of plane strain. The two dimensional stress-strain relationship for orthotropic materials can be written as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_1 \\ \epsilon_2 \\ \gamma_{12} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} b_{11} & b_{12} & 0 \\ b_{12} & b_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & b_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \tau_{12} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where 1-2 system is the local coordinate attached at the crack tip. Coordinate 1 is made to coincide with fiber direction. The quantities σ_1 , σ_2 , τ_{12} and ϵ_1 , ϵ_2 , γ_{12} are the inplane stresses and strains, and b_{ij} are the compliance coefficients. The stress and displacement fields u , v in 1, 2 directions in the vicinity of the crack tip are given by [4]:

$$\sigma_1 = \frac{k_1}{\sqrt{2r}} \operatorname{Re} \left[\frac{\mu_1 \mu_2}{\mu_1 - \mu_2} (\mu_2 F_2 - \mu_1 F_1) \right] + \frac{k_2}{\sqrt{2r}} \operatorname{Re} \left[\frac{1}{\mu_1 - \mu_2} (\mu_2^2 F_2 - \mu_1^2 F_1) \right] \quad (2a)$$

$$\sigma_2 = \frac{k_1}{\sqrt{2r}} \operatorname{Re} \left[\frac{1}{\mu_1 - \mu_2} (\mu_1 F_2 - \mu_2 F_1) \right] + \frac{k_2}{\sqrt{2r}} \operatorname{Re} \left[\frac{1}{\mu_1 - \mu_2} (F_2 - F_1) \right] \quad (2b)$$

$$\tau_{12} = \frac{k_1}{\sqrt{2r}} \operatorname{Re} \left[\frac{\mu_1 \mu_2}{\mu_1 - \mu_2} (F_1 - F_2) \right] + \frac{k_1}{\sqrt{2r}} \operatorname{Re} \left[\frac{1}{\mu_1 - \mu_2} (\mu_1 F_1 - \mu_2 F_2) \right] \quad (2c)$$

and

$$u = k_1 \sqrt{2r} \operatorname{Re} \left[\frac{1}{\mu_1 - \mu_2} \left(\frac{\mu_1 p_2}{F_2} - \frac{\mu_2 p_1}{F_1} \right) \right] + k_2 \sqrt{2r} \operatorname{Re} \left[\frac{1}{\mu_1 - \mu_2} \left(\frac{p_2}{F_2} - \frac{p_1}{F_1} \right) \right] \quad (3a)$$

$$v = k_1 \sqrt{2r} \operatorname{Re} \left[\frac{1}{\mu_1 - \mu_2} \left(\frac{\mu_1 q_2}{F_2} - \frac{\mu_2 q_1}{F_1} \right) \right] + k_2 \sqrt{2r} \operatorname{Re} \left[\frac{1}{\mu_1 - \mu_2} \left(\frac{q_2}{F_2} - \frac{q_1}{F_1} \right) \right] \quad (3b)$$

where the parameters $p_{1,2}$, $q_{1,2}$ and $F_{1,2}$ are

$$p_{1,2} = \mu_{1,2}^2 b_{11} + b_{12} \quad (4)$$

$$q_{1,2} = \mu_{1,2} b_{12} + \frac{b_{22}}{\mu_{1,2}} \quad (5)$$

$$F_{1,2} = (\cos \theta + \mu_{1,2} \sin \theta)^{-1/2} \quad (6)$$

The parameters μ_1 and μ_2 are the roots of the fourth order characteristic equation.

$$\mu^4 + 2\chi\mu^2 + \lambda^2 = 0 \quad (7)$$

The solutions can be obtained as

$$\mu_{1,2} = \frac{i}{\sqrt{2}} \left[(\chi + \lambda)^{1/2} \pm (\chi - \lambda)^{1/2} \right] = \omega_{1,2} i \quad (8)$$

where

$$\lambda^2 = \frac{b_{22}}{b_{11}}, \quad \chi = \frac{2b_{12} + b_{66}}{2b_{11}} \quad (9)$$

From eqns. (2) - (9), the relations between the displacement components u , v at the crack surface ($\theta = \pm\pi$) and the stress intensity factors are

$$k_1 = \left(\frac{1}{2r} \right)^{1/2} \frac{\omega_1 \omega_2}{(\omega_1 + \omega_2) b_{22}} v \quad (10)$$

$$k_2 = \left(\frac{1}{2r} \right)^{1/2} \frac{1}{(\omega_1 + \omega_2) b_{11}} u \quad (11)$$

After performing the finite element analysis, the stress intensity factors are computed from the results of displacement components by using a \sqrt{r} linear extrapolation [9]. In order to apply the strain energy density theory to predict the crack propagation [10], the variations of the minimum strain energy density factor S_{\min} along the crack border will be calculated. The first hypothesis of the theory states that the direction θ_0 of the crack propagation at any point along the crack border is toward the region with the minimum value of strain energy density factor S . The second hypothesis is that the crack extension occurs when the minimum factor S_{\min} reaches a critical material value S_{cr} . The factor S can be expressed as

$$S = A_{11} k_1^2 + 2A_{12} k_1 k_2 + A_{22} k_2^2 \quad (12)$$

where

$$A_{11} = \frac{1}{4} (b_{11} A^2 + b_{22} C^2 + b_{66} E^2 + 2b_{12} AC) \quad (13a)$$

$$A_{12} = \frac{1}{4} [b_{11} AB + b_{22} CD + b_{66} EF + b_{12} (AD + BC)] \quad (13b)$$

$$A_{22} = \frac{1}{4} (b_{11} B^2 + b_{22} D^2 + b_{66} F^2 + 2b_{12} BD) \quad (13c)$$

and

$$A = \operatorname{Re} \left[\frac{\mu_1 \mu_2}{\mu_1 - \mu_2} (\mu_2 F_2 - \mu_1 F_1) \right] \quad (14a)$$

$$B = \operatorname{Re} \left[\frac{1}{\mu_1 - \mu_2} (\mu_2^2 F_2 - \mu_1^2 F_1) \right] \quad (14b)$$

$$C = \operatorname{Re} \left[\frac{1}{\mu_1 - \mu_2} (\mu_1 F_2 - \mu_2 F_1) \right] \quad (14c)$$

$$D = \operatorname{Re} \left[\frac{1}{\mu_1 - \mu_2} (F_2 - F_1) \right] \quad (14d)$$

$$E = \operatorname{Re} \left[\frac{1}{\mu_1 - \mu_2} (F_2 - F_1) \right] \quad (14e)$$

$$F = \operatorname{Re} \left[\frac{1}{\mu_1 - \mu_2} (\mu_1 F_1 - \mu_2 F_2) \right] \quad (14f)$$

FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

The configuration of the bonded repair for cracked plate is shown in Fig. 1. The unidirectional graphite/epoxy composite plate with dimensions 508 mm \times 635 mm \times 2.29 mm contains a 45° inclined central through 38.1 mm crack. The composite plate has principal material axes oriented at $\alpha = 45^\circ$ and is loaded by remote biaxial stresses $\sigma_y = 0.689$ Mpa and $\sigma_x = \lambda \sigma_y$, where λ is the load ratio. The crack is repaired by rectangular or square graphite/epoxy laminae on both sides of the plate. The dimension of each ply of the patch is W mm \times L mm \times 0.254 mm (50.8 mm \times 152.4 mm \times 0.254 mm for rectangular patch and 87.988 mm \times 87.988 mm \times 0.254 mm for square patch). The thickness of the adhesive is 0.1016mm. Table 1 lists the material properties of all components. Because the x-y plane is the symmetric plane, only one half of the structure is needed to be modelled by using three-dimensional 20-node isoparametric brick elements. The region adjacent to the crack front is modelled by singular crack elements. The singular element shifts the side nodes to the quarter-point position to induce the required $1/\sqrt{r}$ stress singularity. The element sides are set along a straight line normal to the crackfront such that k_i 's can be calculated by eqns (10) and (11). Fig. 2 shows a typical finite element mesh. Since the thickness of the element is very small compared with the x-y plane dimensions, the elements in that region should be modelled with a high aspect ratio. To avoid unmerical ill conditioning on these elements, a reduced integration technique [11] has been applied.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Two cases are considered in this report. Case A discusses the effects of loading ratio λ , the patch shape and the patch fiber orientation ϕ on the repair performance. The shapes of the patch are

rectangle and square. Load ratios is taken to be $\lambda = -2, -1, 0, 1, 2$. The fiber orientation ϕ of the patch is $\phi = 0^\circ - 180^\circ$ at 15° interval. Case B discusses the stacking sequence effect. The patch in this case is 3-ply laminated composite with the ply orientation $\phi = 0^\circ, 90^\circ, 135^\circ$. To check the accuracy of the finite element modelling, the computed stress intensity factors of uniaxial loading σ_y ($\lambda = 0$) are compared with existing analytical solutions. The analytical [12] and the finite element solutions are $k_1 = 1.5036\text{Mpa}\sqrt{\text{mm}}$, $k_2 = 1.5036\text{Mpa}\sqrt{\text{mm}}$, and $k_1 = 1.4411\text{Mpa}\sqrt{\text{mm}}$, $k_2 = 1.4710\text{Mpa}\sqrt{\text{mm}}$ respectively. The errors are within 5%. Thus, the finite element modelling approach is proved to give good results.

1. Effects of loading ratio λ , patch shape, and patch fiber orientation ϕ

Rectangular (50.8 mm \times 152.4 mm \times 0.254 mm) and square (87.988 mm \times 87.988 mm \times 0.254 mm) patches are used for analyzing the effects of patch shape on the repair design under different load ratio λ . In general, as $\lambda \geq 2$ for larger apply loading in x direction, rectangular patch has better efficiency. This can be seen in Fig. 3 for typical case $\lambda = 2$. The parameter R_s is defined as the ratio of strain energy density factor S for patched and unpatched cases. Smaller R_s values mean better efficiency. In addition, if the fiber orientation ϕ of the patch is taken to be perpendicular to the crack surface, the design will be the best. As $\lambda \leq 0$, square shape is the better choice. Best fiber orientations ϕ are in y direction, the maximum tensile load direction. Fig. 4 shows the typical case $\lambda = 0$. For the special case $\lambda = 0$, the hydrostatic tension, these two shapes make no much difference and best angle ϕ is 135° .

2. Effects of stacking sequence

There are six satcking sequences of the 3-ply patch with $\phi = 45^\circ, 90^\circ$ and 135° . After performing finite element analyses under $\lambda = -2, -1, 0, 1, 2$, the results of values R_s appear to be almost the same. This shows that the stacking sequences have little influence on the strain energy distribution near the crack tip and the repairing efficiency. Table 2 lists the results for a typical case $\lambda = 0$.

CONCLUSION

Linear elastic fracture mechanics and strain energy density theory have been applied to study the bonded repair on cracked composite components under biaxial loading. The strain energy distribution around the crack tip is found to be almost independent of the stacking sequences of the laminated patch. It is also has been proved that the ply parallel to the crack has a limited contribution to the repair design. Is is suggested that ply orientations 90° and $\pm 45^\circ$ related to the crack direction are the optimal choice in bonded repair.

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Table 1. Material properties used in bonded repair analyses

Components	Material properties
Plate and Patch (Graphite/epoxy)	$E_{11}=141\text{GPa}$, $E_{22}=9.425\text{GPa}$, $E_{33}=9.425\text{GPa}$, $G_{12}=5.18\text{GPa}$, $G_{23}=5.20\text{GPa}$, $G_{13}=5.20\text{GPa}$, $\nu_{12}=0.31$, $\nu_{23}=0.41$, $\nu_{13}=0.31$
Adhesive	$G_a=0.965\text{GPa}$, $\nu_a=0.32$

Table 2. The relations of design parameters for different stacking sequences ($\lambda=0$)

Stacking sequence	k_1 ($\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{mm}}$)	k_2 ($\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{mm}}$)	S_{min} (10^{-2}N/m)	R_s
0 ⁰ /90 ⁰ /135 ⁰	0.07426	0.15254	0.04415	0.00488
0 ⁰ /135 ⁰ /90 ⁰	0.06894	0.15429	0.04206	0.00465
90 ⁰ /0 ⁰ /135 ⁰	0.06802	0.15243	0.04100	0.00453
90 ⁰ /135 ⁰ /0 ⁰	0.06781	0.15209	0.04080	0.00451
135 ⁰ /0 ⁰ /90 ⁰	0.06706	0.15367	0.04094	0.00452
135 ⁰ /90 ⁰ /0 ⁰	0.06697	0.15344	0.04083	0.00451

Figure 1. Configurations of bonded repair for cracked plate.

MARC

Figure 2. The finite element grid pattern of bonded repair for cracked plate.

Figure 3. The variations of R_s at different fiber angle ϕ for rectangular and square patches ($\lambda = 2$)

Figure 4. The variations of R_s at different fiber angle ϕ for rectangular and square patches ($\lambda = 0$)